

The Harvard Expedition to Tepe Yahya,
c/o Maden Ab-Dasht,
Bander Abbas,
Iran,
22/7/71

Dear David,

I'm very sorry that I forgot to leave this note for you when I left Teheran. I hope your work goes well.

I enclose carbons of the documents I gave to Dr. Naimi about Bushehr. The areas of the coast which I am most concerned with for archaeological survey in order of their archaeological priority and interest are as follows:

- 1) The area around Siraf and on the Persian Gulf coast for ⁵⁰~~100~~ kms. on either side of Siraf

I will return to Teheran on or around 18 September by which time I assume you will already be at Qum, + I would be very grateful for any information as to the archaeological services near ^{any} survey on the coast especially - area of Siraf. I intend to ^{fly back} return to Oxford on the 7-10th of November + will be able to discuss these, any necessary changes to my ^{research} work over the next 2 years. It should be very straightforward simply to conduct ^{the} documentary work before fieldwork rather than the other way round as planned + I would hope require any intervention ^{at Oxford} on your part.

22/7/71

Dear David,

I'm very sorry that I forgot to leave this note for you when I left Teheran. I hope your work goes well.

I enclose carbons of the documents I gave to Dr. Naimi about Bushehr. The areas of the coast which I am most concerned with for archaeological survey in order of their archaeological priority and interest are as follows:

- 1) The area around Siraf and on the Persian Gulf coast for ⁵⁰~~100~~ kms. on either side of Siraf

I will return to Teheran on or around 18²⁴ September by which time I assume you will already be at Qum, + I would be very grateful for any information as to the archaeological services near ^{any survey on the coast especially - area} ~~any survey on the coast especially - area~~ of Naqsh-e Rostam. I intend to ^{fly back} ~~return to Oxford~~ ^{on the 7-10th} of November + will be able to discuss there, any necessary changes to my ^{fly back} ~~report~~ ^{over the next 2 years} ~~work~~ ^{conduct} ~~to~~ ^{documentary} ~~work~~ ^{before fieldwork} ~~rather than the other way round as planned + should not require any intervention ~~at Oxford~~ ^{at your place} on your part by yourself on my behalf.~~

Dear David,

I'm very sorry that I forgot to leave this note for you when I left

Lebanon. I hope your work goes well.

I enclose carbon copies of the documents I gave to Mr. Fourn about the

excavation of the coast which I am most concerned with for a chronological survey

in order of their archaeological priority and interest are as follows:

1) The area around Birat and on the Lebanese Gulf coast for 100 years.

on either side of Birat

P.S. if paper Birat ~~is not to be~~ or
~~at the~~ Deyne Meadows are leaving
the Institute for Tife-yahya on 4th August
could you please send my letters down with
them.